

Mode I Fracture Toughness of 3D Composites Reinforced With Metal or Carbon Z-binders

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Introduction and Background

- Fibre-reinforced polymer composites are widely used for aerospace structures.
- High specific strength and stiffness,
- Lightweight,
- Fibre composites have several shortcomings.
- Low through thickness delamination
- Delamination damage in composite structures may be caused by extreme through-thickness interlaminar static and fatigue loads, environmental degradation, or an impact load (e.g. hail stone, bird strike).
- Delamination damage can also reduce the in-plane mechanical properties and create pathways for water and other fluids to insert in the structure, which can further reduce the properties.

<https://www.airliners.net/forum/viewtopic.php?t=1373451>

Methodology

Through-the-thickness weaving

Resin Infusion

Raj B.Ladani et al, 2018

$$G_{IC} = \frac{3P\delta}{2B(a + |d|)}$$

Results

Mode I Fracture Toughness

Pull-out Test

Discussion

Copper z-binder

Carbon z-binder

Steel z-binder

Conclusion

- Through-the-thickness reinforcement using steel, carbon and copper z-binder increased the mode I fracture toughness of the 3D fibre composites by ~7000%, ~2000% and ~500% respectively.
- Low strength z-binders (e.g. copper) plastically deform and fracture under mode I interlaminar loading, causing them to be less effective at delamination toughening than high strength z-binders (e.g. stainless steel and carbon fibre).
- High strength z-binders do not fracture, and instead fail by debonding and sliding pull-out which promotes high delamination toughening.